

Axial compression testing of carbon fibers

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General Introduction

Carbon fibers are widely used as reinforcement in carbon fiber reinforced plastics (CFRP). Recent developments have provided rapid growth in mechanical properties of polyacrylonitrile-(PAN) based carbon fibers. Now, tensile strength is to 7 GPa is available in PAN-based carbon carbon fiber multifilaments. When a CFRP plate is subjected to bending, for example, both tensile and compression stresses arise and the compression strength, not the tensile strength, determines the loading capacity. The improvement of axial compression strength of CFRP requires promoting compression strength of carbon fibers [1]. Measurements of the axial compression strength of carbon fibers are much difficult than the tensile strength. There have been developed several methods for determining single fiber axial compression strength such as loop test [2] tensile recoil test [3] and direct single fiber test [4]. However, the test dates of these methods are much lower than expectation. In this study, the axial compression strength of carbon fiber multifilament has been determined on a series PAN-based carbon fibers using bundle compression test similar to the compression measurement of unidirectional laminated composites. This test allows for rapid response and utilizes smaller amounts of material for initial screening testing.

Keywords: carbon fiber, multifilament, compression strength, testing * Corresponding author (fengzhh2006@sina.com)

Specimen Preparation and Test Method

- Tow compression specimen consists of an impregnated bundle carbon fibers surrounded by a resin tab(Fig.1). Impregnation is accomplished by placing a tube dry carbon fiber though a automatic mechanical sample preparation machine. The compression specimen is placed into a mold, which also acts as the test fixture. Apply the force to the fixture at the specified rate until failure while recording date(Fig.2).

Fig.1. Schematic of tow compression specimen

Fig.2. Schematic of fixture setup

Calculation of Results

- Calculate the ultimate compression strength using equations 1.
- $F = P/A$ (1)
- Where:
- F = compression strength, MPa,
- P = failure force, N,
- A = cross-sectional area at fiber section, mm^2 .
- The cross-sectional area at fiber section is calculated using equations 2
- $A = l/\rho$ (2)
- Where:
- l = linear density, g/m, ρ = fiber density, g/cm^3 .

Results and Discussion

- The axial compression strength was much lower than the tensile strength. It is also seen that the coefficient of variation of compression strength was higher than the tensile strength. Usually, measurements of the tensile strength are commonly practiced as one of the most fundamental mechanical tests for the quality control. However, there are many unsure factors influencing the instability of compression stress. Nevertheless, these results of compression strength were still acceptable.

Tab.1 Axial compression strength values in PAN-based carbon fibers

Fiber grade	Yield /K	Compression strength /MPa	Tensile strength /MPa
T300B	6	2260(6.2)*	3655(3.2)
T700S	12	2523(7.8)	5180(2.8)
T800H	12	2835(5.0)	5630(2.5)
T800S	24	2229(6.6)	5910(3.6)
T1000	12	2462(6.2)	6410(2.7)
M40J	6	2431(4.5)	4502(3.5)
M55J	6	1886(6.8)	4062(4.2)

*Coefficient of variation (%) in parentheses.

- SEM observations were applied for compressed carbon fiber multifilament. The compression section of the specimen presented shear failure morphology with an angle. For these carbon fibers(particularly for M55J), kink bands appeared on the surface as shown in Fig.3. The kink bands usually developed into splitting failure along the specimen axis.

Fig.3 Failure mode of multifilament specimen

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